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ABSTRACT

The objective of the Task was to analyze spontaneous flora communities across the project European Case Studies (CSs) and assess their potential for C sequestration in the context of agroecological (AE) intensification. The study specifically investigated the distribution of diversity indices and functional traits related to C sequestration to test hypotheses that:

1. the response of spontaneous flora would vary according to the specific pedoclimatic conditions of each site;
2. these communities would have higher diversity and lower dominance in response to agroecological intensification;
3. agroecological intensification would enhance carbon sequestration potential of spontaneous flora communities.

Each project CS employ different systems and treatments. Treatments were categorized by varying agroecological practices: T1 (low AE intensification), T2 (high AE intensification), and T3 (control, with no AE intensification). Spontaneous flora assessments were performed at two phenological stages, representing minimum and maximum plant nutrient uptake, to understand temporal variations and to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem's carbon sequestration potential, as it reflects both the peak carbon assimilation period (spring - MAX) and the period of carbon storage and resource conservation (late summer - MIN).

By using a trait-based analysis, we selected key plants' characteristics such as canopy height (CH), specific leaf area (SLA), % of grass-like species, supporting arbuscular mycorrhiza and perennials. These traits are linked to mechanisms by means plants can provide C sequestration, including biomass productivity and quality, investment in C storage structures in the soil and mycorrhizal associations. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey tests, confirmed significant differences in trait values between treatments. In cases where binary data were present, Chi-square tests and Fisher's Exact Test provided insights into species distribution and functional trait prevalence.

Our findings indicated that, in according to our first hypothesis, ecological and environmental variables significantly shaped spontaneous flora communities, often overshadowing the effects of intensification treatments. For instance, agroforestry systems (e.g., CS1 and CS3) demonstrated higher species richness and greater structural diversity compared to arable and vegetable systems. The reduced soil disturbance and shaded microenvironments in these systems supported a more diverse flora, enhancing ecosystem functions like C sequestration through stable root systems and increased organic matter inputs.

IN CS1 higher SLA and canopy height in no-till treatment was also found at the MAX stage, as well as in no-till CS5 treatments, aligning with increased aboveground biomass potential. Meanwhile, in vegetable systems like CS8, cover crops and fungi inoculation influenced SLA traits, albeit within a narrow range, demonstrating the need for optimal environmental conditions to maximize growth and C input.

In no-till treatments (e.g., T1 in CS1 and T1 and T2 in CS5 and CS7), SAM species were also favored, leading to greater mycorrhizal colonization and improved soil structure.

Trait analysis also revealed that grass-like species in undisturbed systems can contribute to soil organic C storage, emphasizing the role of root exudates and decomposing matter in forming stable soil aggregates. These systems seemed to show a functional profile akin to natural ecosystems, where stable plant communities optimize C storage. This contrasts with tilled environments, where annual and pioneer species dominate due to frequent soil disturbance, disrupting microbial networks essential for C sequestration. However, in some cases, such as CS9, low species richness and limited trait variation suggested that organic matter management alone may not suffice without broader ecosystem management strategies. No clear trends were found for the perennial trait among CSs.

The research demonstrates that spontaneous flora, traditionally seen as a hindrance in agriculture, can be strategically managed to enhance soil health and carbon dynamics. By integrating these plant

communities into agroecological practices, farmers can promote a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system. The results underscore the complexity of interactions between plant traits, management practices, and environmental conditions, highlighting the need for site-specific strategies to maximize ecosystem benefits.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
CS	Case study
CH	Canopy height
SLA	Specific Leaf Area
SAM	Supporting Arbuscular Mycorrhiza
CWM	Community-level Weighted Mean

1. Introduction

The role of spontaneous flora, often referred to as weeds, has traditionally been viewed as antagonistic to agricultural productivity. However, recent studies have highlighted their potential benefits, particularly in contributing to ecosystem services such as enhancing soil health, supporting biodiversity, regulating water cycles, and facilitating carbon sequestration (Barberi et al., 2018; Ciaccia et al., 2022). These contributions are gaining importance in the context of agroecological intensification, which aims to increase agricultural sustainability by optimizing ecological processes within farming systems (Wezel et al., 2015).

The carbon sequestration potential of spontaneous flora is linked to several mechanisms. Firstly, through the above ground biomass productivity and related organic matter inputs to soil (Alonso-Serra, J. (2021). Moreover, these plants can contribute to the formation of soil aggregates, which protect organic carbon from decomposition, thus promoting long-term carbon storage in soils. Additionally, spontaneous flora often thrives in less disturbed soils, where they can enhance microbial activity and nutrient cycling, further supporting soil carbon sequestration processes (Ilic, 2023).

Spontaneous flora can promote soil cover, reducing erosion and the loss of organic matter, which is essential for maintaining soil carbon stocks. Moreover, their roots can contribute to the accumulation of organic carbon in the soil, particularly in the form of root exudates and decaying plant matter.

In agroecological intensification, managing spontaneous flora is essential. Rather than viewing them solely as competitors to crops, there is a shift towards managing them as functional components of agricultural ecosystems (Gaba et al., 2014). By integrating spontaneous flora, farmers can enhance biodiversity, improve soil health, reduce chemical inputs, and contribute to carbon sequestration.

2. Executive summary (if required)

This study analyzed the role of spontaneous flora communities across various European Case Studies (CSs) in enhancing carbon (C) sequestration within agroecological intensification frameworks. The primary objective was to examine diversity indices and functional traits related to C sequestration to evaluate if:

- i) spontaneous flora communities respond variably to site-specific soil and climate conditions,
- ii) agroecological intensification promotes higher biodiversity and lower species dominance, and
- iii) intensification practices enhance the C sequestration potential of these flora communities.

Each CS implemented different agricultural systems and AE treatments categorized into low agroecological intensification (T1), high agroecological intensification (T2), and control (T3, with no agroecological intensification). Flora assessments were conducted at two key growth stages to capture both peak carbon assimilation and carbon storage phases. By focusing on traits such as canopy height, specific leaf area, grass-like species prevalence, arbuscular mycorrhizal presence, and perennial status, the study identified traits that contribute to C sequestration through biomass productivity, carbon storage structures, and mycorrhizal associations.

Key findings revealed that ecological and environmental variables significantly shaped flora community structures, often more than intensification practices. For example, agroforestry systems displayed higher species richness and structural diversity, promoting stable root systems and organic matter accumulation favorable to C sequestration. In no-till treatments, spontaneous flora exhibited traits beneficial to soil health, like greater mycorrhizal colonization which supports soil carbon storage.

The research underscores that spontaneous flora, often seen as a challenge in conventional agriculture, can be a strategic asset in agroecological practices. Integrating these communities can improve soil health, enhance carbon dynamics, and support sustainable agriculture. This study highlights the complexity of interactions between plant traits, management practices, and environmental conditions, advocating for tailored, site-specific approaches to maximize ecosystem benefits in agricultural landscapes.

3. Main text

3.1. Materials and methods

Case studies and treatments

The case studies participating to the task assessments and the treatments in comparison in each of them are reported in Table 1. The compared treatments were classified according to the level of agroecological intensification introduced, as follows:

T1 = lower agroecological intensification

T2 = higher agroecological intensification

T3 = no agroecological intensification (control)

The case studies addressed agroecological intensification differently in their comparative systems, each working on different agroecosystems and practices tailored to their specific contexts. Table 1 summarizes the strategies introduced with respect to the controls.

Table 1 – AGROECOseqC Case studies participating to the Task 2.1 assessments and treatments in comparison.

Case study	System	Treatments	Code	Agroecological intensification
CS1 (CREA)	Organic fruit orchard	INC - compost, no tillage , spontaneous cover	T1	Cover crop/soil tillage
		ICC - compost, tillage, mixed cover crops	T2	
		BAU -tillage, organic fertilizer, no CC (Control)	T3	
CS2 (INRAE - CF)	Arable	GLN - grasses, legumes - new system	T1	Mixture of spring wheat with a diversified perennial herbaceous cover
		WGLN - spring wheat, grasses, legumes - new system	T2	
		WN - spring wheat - new system (Control)	T3	
CS3 (INRAE -MP)	Agroforestry (tree + arables)	TSG - Tree strip + perennial grass, no tillage	T2	Agroforestry
		TSR - Crop rotation in agroforestry alley, tillage (Control)	T3	
CS5 (CSIC-INIA)	Arable	No tillage, wheat	T1	Diversification of rotation/soil tillage
		No tillage, rotation (wheat-vetch-barley)	T2	
		Minimum tillage, wheat (Control)	T3	
CS7 (LAMMC)	Arable	NT - No tillage without cover crops	T1	Soil tillage/cover crops
		NT + CC - No tillage + cover crops	T2	

		T - Conventional tillage without cover crops (Control)	T3	
CS8 (TAGEM)	Vegetable	NFC - No fungi inoculum with cover crop	T1	Cover crops/fungi inoculum
		FC - Fungi inoculum with cover crop	T2	
		NFNC - No fungi inoculum without cover crop (Control)	T3	
CS9 (CRAW)	Arable	SBWBFYM - Sugar beet, wheat, barley, farmyard manure	T1	Organic matter management/manure application/cover crops
		SBWBCR - Sugar beet, wheat, barley, crop res. restitution and cover crop	T2	
		SBWB - Sugar beet, wheat, barley, residue exportation (Control)	T3	

Spontaneous flora assessments

According to the instructions reported in the AGROECOseqC Handbook, in each case study, by-species vegetational surveys were conducted at two phenological stages of the experiments, corresponding to minimum (MIN) and maximum (MAX) plant nutrient uptake. Spontaneous flora communities (i.e. by-species density or coverage) were analysed following a trait analysis approach. We considered the main mechanisms through which plant community may drive C sequestration in agroecosystems and plant functional characteristics (i.e. traits) linked to these drivers were selected and their distribution in the communities was studied. Cover (or density) assessments allowed to provide diversity indices: species richness, R (number of species per m² per treatment) and Evenness. Evenness (Magurran, 1988) was based on the Pielou index as: H/H_{max} , where H is Shannon-Weaver index [1] and H_{max} is the base-e logarithm of R.

$$H = -\sum_{i=1}^R p_i * \ln(p_i) \quad [1]$$

where:

“ P_i ” = proportion of a given species relative to the total number of species found in the i-th sample.

“ $\ln P_i$ ” = natural logarithm of P_i .

“R” = number of species found in the i-th sample.

Trait selection

Plant traits were selected from the weed functional traits database published by Barberi et al. (2018) and from literature (Kattge et al., 2020), on the base of their potential ecological role in sequestering C and potential response to management. The analysed traits were: canopy height (CH, m; maximum height at maturity), specific leaf area (SLA, mm² mg⁻¹), grass and grass-like species (Grass, %), life form (perennials, %; perennials vs annuals); Supporting Arbuscular Mycorrhiza (SAM, %).

Several studies have shown that CH and SLA are indeed good indicators of biomass development in vegetation (Walter et al., 2019), therefore indicators of the potential contribution of the species to C input to the soil. CH is often used as a proxy to estimate aboveground biomass, as it reflects the structure and density of vegetation. Similarly, SLA, which measures leaf area relative to dry mass, is correlated with plant productivity, as it indicates how efficiently a plant can capture light for photosynthesis and, consequently, produce biomass. Grass and grass-like species are known to contribute to soil C input with a higher carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio, which is linked to more stable soil organic matter. Perennial species tend to contribute more to soil carbon storage than annuals due to their larger and more persistent root systems. This allows perennials to store carbon deeper in the soil and for a longer duration. Studies highlight those perennial plants, with their extensive root systems and slow decomposition rates of root material, enhance soil carbon sequestration compared

to annual plants (Dessureault-Rompré, 2022). Their roots, along with propagules, act as significant carbon sinks, helping to stabilize organic matter in the soil. Finally, SAM% is related to the potential attraction (and presence) of mycorrhiza in the plant-soil system, suggesting a potential greater mycelial network development in the soil,

Statistical analysis

Community-level weighted mean of trait values (CWM), which measures the weighted average of traits for the species pool in the weed community, was calculated for each single trait. For categorical traits, only one of the levels was analysed, i.e., perennial weeds CWM was analyzed for the Perennials. To assess whether there are significant differences between treatments within each site, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed for each site across different sampling times. The goal of the analysis was to determine if the treatment effects varied significantly at different times and to identify which treatments were significantly different from each other. For each sampling time within each core site, a one-way ANOVA was conducted, where the several functional traits represent the response variable, and treatment is the factor of interest. The *aov* function in R was used for this analysis.

If the ANOVA results indicated significant differences between treatments (p -value < 0.05), a post-hoc Tukey HSD test was conducted to identify which specific treatments were significantly different from each other. This test is appropriate for multiple pairwise comparisons to control for Type I error.

In cases where ANOVA could not be applied because the data were binary (e.g., presence/absence data), a Chi-square test was used to compare treatments within each core site to determine if there were significant differences. For each sampling time, a contingency table was created using binary data (e.g., presence of "Taproot") and treatments. If the contingency table met the criteria for a valid Chi-square test, the test was performed using the *chisq.test* function in R. If the Chi-square test showed significant differences between treatments (p -value < 0.05), Fisher's Exact Test was conducted to provide a more accurate assessment of the differences.

3.2. Results and Discussion

Diversity indices

The results on diversity indices are reported in Figure 1.

b)

Figure 1. Boxplots for a) Richness and b) Evenness at maximum (MAX) and minimum (MIN) plant nutrient uptake stage for the case studies in comparison.

Probability level: *, $p \leq 0.05$; **, $p \leq 0.01$; ***, $p \leq 0.001$.

As expected, the ecological, environmental, and management-specific variables of each case study seem to dominate on a larger scale, leading to a clustering of biodiversity indices' values by case study. This suggests that local conditions exert a stronger influence on biodiversity than the treatments applied. Highest values of species Richness were found in CS1 at Max and CS3 (even with high variability in this last case) in T2 at both MAX and MIN stage, both CSs representing the inter-row of tree systems (agroforestry systems). Agroforestry systems generally offer greater structural diversity than arable and horticultural systems. This diversity creates variable microenvironments such as shade and less disturbed soils, which favor a greater richness of spontaneous species (Santos et al., 2022). Moreover, less intensive soil management, without frequent ploughing and weeding than arable and horticultural systems, allows for a more lasting colonization of spontaneous species, especially those sensitive to disturbance. These factors seem to have created an environment more suitable for the establishment and coexistence of a wider range of spontaneous species respect the other CSs. The mean values of the Pielou index were greater than 0.5 for most treatments across the different case studies, indicating a relatively equal distribution of species with no dominance. This condition is often associated with greater ecological stability and good habitat quality, indicating a not intensive management of the CSs.

Analysing each individual case study, in CS1 higher R values were recorded at MAX (spring) than MIN (late summer), when more variety of microclimates allows different species to coexist and lower stress favours more species. At MAX, significantly higher values of R were found in T1 and T3 than T2, due to the dominance of the cover crop which reduces the coexisting plant ecological niches. No significant differences were found between tilled T3 and no tilled T1. Significantly higher E value was found in T3 than T2 and T1, probably due to the superficial tillage which have reasonably made the soil and the distribution of resources more homogeneous for the growth of specie. At MIN, no significant differences of the indices were found in the compared treatments.

In CS2, although moving within a range of low values, R was lower in T2 then T1 and T3 at both MAX and MIN (at MIN no species were found in T2), same was found for the E values, even if just as trend. In a more diversified system, we would expect a greater variety of microclimates and habitats that favour a greater presence of spontaneous species. Instead, here, the interaction deriving from the association of wheat and the mix in the perennial cover in T2 have reasonably created a more competitive environment for resources, discouraging the presence of less competitive spontaneous

species. As second hypothesis, the synergistic association of the crop species in T2 could have resulted in an increased development of the cover that prevented the establishment of spontaneous species. In CS3, R was higher in no tilled T2 than T3 at MIN, with no species recorded at MAX in T3 due to weeding after MIN sampling. Tillage, in combination with the intensification of the inter-row management, seems to have reduced R resulting in a more disturbed and competitive system, with a complete dominance of wheat. E values at MIN were not significantly different among the two systems.

In CS5, at MAX, R was significantly higher in the control than the no tilled T2 and T1, contrary to what happened in CS2. Soil tillage, if not managed as an excessive disturbance factor, can effectively act in releasing new ecological niches and stimulate the germination of the soil seedbank (Feledyn-Szewczyk et al., 2020), favouring species richness in the short term. At MIN, the communities were similar in terms of R and E in the compared treatments, probably due to the dominating effect of the environmental stress conditions (semi-arid conditions in the specific CS) at MIN on the comparative factors.

Contrary to CS5, but in line with CS3, in CS7 no tilled systems recorded significantly higher R than the tilled control at both MAX and MIN, especially in combination with cover crops (T2), even if at MIN no species were found in T3 due to previous ploughing. E indicator was also significantly higher in T2 than T1 at MIN. No till management, carried on since 2003, probably led to the establishment of equilibrium conditions leading to greater diversity of spontaneous species (Testani et al., 2019). However, in CS7, unfortunately, it should be noted that a significant development of the volunteer oilseed rape (previous crop, not considered as spontaneous plant in this study) has probably greatly influenced the development of spontaneous flora communities, both in terms of diversity and traits.

In C8, the three systems recorded similar values of R and E at MAX with no effect exerted by cover crops and fungi inoculum, while, as a trend, communities were richer in species with higher evenness in the treatments with cover crop respect to the control at MIN, even if within a narrow range of values. Effectively, by improving soil conditions and, thus, creating more favourable microenvironments, cover crops can promote the germination and growth of a wider range of spontaneous species in vegetable systems leading to a more balanced community.

Finally, in C9, similar and low values of R were found at both MAX and MIN, highlighting no significant effect of the organic matter input and management on spontaneous flora in the specific context.

C sequestration-related traits

The analysis of the traits linked to C sequestration potential by the spontaneous flora communities in the different project CSs are reported in Figure 2. For all the traits considered, the higher their value, the greater the potential for C sequestration according to the mechanism that the trait represents.

Figure 2. Boxplots for a) Specific Leaf area (SLA); b) Canopy height; c) Supporting Arbuscular Mycorrhiza (SAM) %; d) Grass-like %; e) Perennials % at maximum (MAX) and minimum (MIN) plant nutrient uptake stage for the case studies in comparison.

Probability level: *, $p \leq 0.05$; **, $p \leq 0.01$; ***, $p \leq 0.001$.

Ecological phenomena often produce very varied and scattered data, therefore, most of the following considerations refer to observed trends, since significance among treatments' differences were found in few cases.

As for the diversity indices, trait values also seemed to cluster by case study in some cases, highlighting the strong effect of the local conditions on flora communities and on the strength of the potential ecosystem services provisioning.

In CS1, it is interesting to observe that all the analyzed traits, showed higher mean values at MIN, this result suggesting that the community is more driven towards C sequestration than the community recorded at MAX. This effect is not observable in the other case studies, where in most cases the average values of each trait are similar over the two sampling times. At MAX no tilled system recorded different and higher values than T2 and T3, with significant difference in all the cases. In an agroecosystem with little disturbance like no tilled T1, spontaneous flora community seems to organize itself similarly to that of natural systems, notoriously effective in sequestering C according to the mechanisms analyzed here. On the other hand, it is well known that, when the soil is not tilled, a more stable and less disturbed environment is created, which favors perennial and grass-like species (Ciaccia et al., 2022) that form deep and extensive roots, and that compete well in less dynamic and more established environments. Grasses, with their fascicled root systems, are particularly efficient at colonizing spaces without major disturbance, as they do not have to compete with species that thrive on tilled soils. In the untilled soils, perennial species are more prone to develop mycorrhizal associations than annual species (Tiane et al., 2024). Perennials, being stable for long periods, offer mycorrhizal fungi a constant source of carbohydrates (from photosynthesis) and a longer-lasting root environment. This stimulates the growth and spread of mycorrhizal fungi. Tilling, on the other hand, promotes annual or pioneer species, which tend to have short life cycles and weaker relationships with mycorrhizae, as they do not guarantee a stable long-term symbiotic relationship. Moreover, Mycorrhiza-forming plants benefit from increased nutrient uptake, especially in undisturbed soils where nutrient availability is often more limited and less accessible than in tilled soils, where mineralization is accelerated by increased soil aeration. At MIN plant demand, no clear treatments behavior is observable.

In CS2, at both MAX and MIN, there is no clear pattern in trait distribution among treatments. Species recorded were almost perennial grass in all the treatments (*Lolium perenne*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Festuca arundinacea* and *Holcus mollis*). Perennial grasses are plant species highly competitive and, therefore, it is reasonable to find them in competitive environments such as during wheat cycle. These types of systems thus seem to work in the direction of good C input and C storage in the underground biomass by the spontaneous flora, but without any differences between them.

In CS3, as no spontaneous species were recorded at MAX in T3, an evaluation of the effect of treatments of communities' traits is not possible at this sampling time. At MIN, the only traits with a significant trend are SLA and SAM, whose values are higher in T3 than T2, highlighting a community more able to provide C input to the soil and support C storage through fungi community in the control. These results are in contrast with those found in the no tilled CS1 system. The perennials percentage is higher in no tilled T2 as expected, but with a slight trend.

In CS5, at both MAX and MIN, no till practice seems to exert similar effect of T1 in CS1 on plant community traits, even if in a completely different system (fruit vs arable). Indeed, except grass-like % and perennials %, all the other traits recorded higher values in T1 and T2, and then in T3. Perennials % at MAX was higher in T3, due to the presence of *Convolvulus arvensis* not recorded in T1 and T3. The *Convolvulus* is a climbing species that finds in the stems of the wheat a good support to develop. In this case, the soil tillage may have favored it further, leading to the breakage of propagules, stimulating his vegetative regeneration. The diversification of the rotation in T2 seems not to have acted on community traits.

In CS7, at MAX, again, the tillage appears as the dominant factor influencing the functionality of the spontaneous flora communities. Regardless of the introduction of cover crops, in both no tilled systems the communities better support mycorrhization and provide higher quality C inputs (higher grass-like %) than the tilled control. AT MIN, no species were recorded in the control, which was indeed ploughed in autumn 2022. Grass-like % and SLA were the only traits that showed differences between the two treatments, being highest in T1.

In CS8, the only vegetable system, traits values are quite similar among treatments. At MAX, a slight trend sees the T2 (cover crops and fungi inoculum) with higher SLA and CH values. In better environmental conditions due to the fungi inoculation, such as an optimal nutrient availability, plants with higher canopy height and higher SLA can capitalize, resulting in greater growth and competitive success. This results in an increased potential for C input to the soil, due to the development of biomass. At MIN, this effect is not observable, anyway the control seems to have higher presence of grass-like species.

In CS9 due to low species richness values, trait movements are unclear and do not provide a clear direction in the C sequestration.

3.3. Conclusions

This study explored the effect of different levels of agroecological intensification on spontaneous flora communities and their functional traits related to carbon sequestration potential in various agroecosystems across Europe. The analyses conducted showed that the ecological and environmental variables specific to the different case studies had a significant influence on biodiversity and community composition, often overriding the effects of the agroecological treatments applied. In agroforestry systems, the introduction of greater structural diversity favored greater wild species richness, while intensive management generally reduced diversity, as observed in arable and vegetable systems.

At the same time, disturbance of the system - here mainly as tillage intensity – seems to promote a functional profile of spontaneous flora more oriented towards carbon sequestration, based on the mechanisms considered and the selected functional traits. This trend is especially evident in systems

with richer species communities, such as in CS1, where the study of species dynamics shows clearer patterns.

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